

Bentonites for chemical industries[†]

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Abstract : Bentonite deposits of major importance occur in association with volcanic rocks, tuffs and tuffaceous sediments of Miocene and Oligocene age, The bentonite layers and veins indicate the bentonization of the tuff having 1–2 mt thickness of the beds. The chemical composition of bentonites are SiO₂ (50–60%), Al₂O₃ (17%), Fe₂O₃, FeO, MgO, CaO, Na₂O, K₂O and traces of TiO₂ and cation exchange capacity value of bentonites are around 98 meq/100 g. Due to the presence of exchangeable cations, the important applications are decolourising oil, manufacture of catalyst, production of oil well drilling muds softening of hard water and suitability of decontamination of radioactive wastes. Bentonites have been found a good adsorbent of hexavalent chromium and arsenic up to permissible limit. Maximum removal of Cr^{VI} takes place at 120 mt. First order kinetics is followed in the case of adsorption of Cr^{VI} and As^{III} by bentonites. This can be exploited on large scale in industry for decontamination of water pollutants.

In view of individual properties, characterization of bentonite has been done using PXRD, TGA, DSC and IR studies. In the OH-stretching region obtained from FTIR, the bands (3600–3690 cm⁻¹) represent surface OH and inner OH. Investigations on thermal behaviour presented a total weight loss of 14.4953%, 19.2160%, 9.8243% and 3.6774% for different samples showing loss of molecular water and dehydroxylation.

The PXRD analysis important for the clay minerals make understand the diffraction characteristics of bentonites. The proportion of montmorillonite layers is abundant in the inner part, but at the margin the layers of Kaolin are present shown in RHB₅, RHB₆, RB₈, RB₉ and RB₁₀ samples.

The chemical formula has been obtained as (Na,Ca)_{0.3}(Al,Mg)₂ SiO₄O₁₀(OH)₂.nH₂O unit indicating montmorillonite.

Keywords : Bentonite, PXRD, TGA, adsorbent, cation exchange capacity.

Introduction

Geological formation

Bentonite deposits of major economic importance occur in association with volcanic rocks, tuffs and tuffaceous sediments of Miocene and Oligocene age. The genesis of the deposits is from :

- (i) Alteration from rhyolitic ash in a marine environment.
- (ii) Hydrothermal alteration from rhyolite and rhyolitic tuff.

It appears that much of the silica and alkali was

leached from the tuff and other rocks by solution during alteration.

The rocks fragments are entirely altered to clayey materials exhibiting a deep bluish-green colour, becomes gray to black in day light within 1 h. It turns brown within a few weeks^{1–3}. The fragments are usually brown in colour on exposed surfaces in the field. The thickness of bentonite bed mined is 1–2 m. The blue colour with benzidine solution indicates the presence of montmorillonite unit⁴.

The chemical formula of montmorillonite is

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$(\text{Na,Ca})_{0.3}(\text{Al,Mg})_2 \text{SiO}_4\text{O}_{10}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$, named after its discovery locality at Montmorillon, 70 km NNW of Limoges, France^{5,6}.

Investigations in the clay minerals clearly shows the dominance of montmorillonites, illite montmorillonite randomly mixed layers. Small amounts of kaolinite were also distributed along with montmorillonite.

The clay minerals have layered structure based on sheets of 6-members rings of silica tetrahedral formed by condensation of sheets of silica tetrahedral with sheets of Al or Mg octahedral⁷⁻⁹. The chemical composition of montmorillonites is as follows : SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 , Fe_2O_3 , FeO , MnO , MgO , CaO , Na_2O and K_2O CEC values in meq/100 g are around 100. Exchangeable cations are Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} .

Cation exchange capacity may be represented as

M^+ - Cation, H^+ - Cation

M^+ exchange, H^+ cation and BH is an exchanger.

$$K = \frac{[\text{BM}][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{BH}][\text{M}^+]}$$

where K is thermodynamic equilibrium constant.

The exchange property of bentonites has novel application in softening of hard water. Bentonite minerals are of industrial use e.g. softening of hard water, wine industry, radioactive wastes, refining of oil and grilling mud in oil wells. The industries are exploiting the vast resource of the bentonites widely distributed in India and other countries. These uses can be attributed to its good adsorption capacity, cation exchange capacity and swelling power^{10,11}.

The problem of fluoride, arsenic and chromium in drinking water in the Gangetic plain is the cause of concern to the environmentalists. Adsorbents used are flyash, coal, activated alumina and agricultural wastes. Among the clays, bentonite is an eco-friendly low cost adsorbent for the removal of arsenic, chro-

Fig. 1. TGA and DTA of sample – RB8.

mium and fluoride. The process of removal of these toxic substances are due to cation exchange capacity and adsorption both. The minerals can be a suitable alternative to the conventional methods for decontamination of the toxic elements from aqueous medium^{12,13}.

Results and discussion

The mineral characterization by this method was found to agree with the results obtained by other methods. It can also be concluded that Jharkhand samples are typically montmorillonite and some samples are illitic.

TGA and DSC studies of the collected samples were analyzed. The investigation of thermal behavior of the bentonite shows a total loss of mass about 14.4953%, 19.2160%, 9.8243% and 3.6774% between 296 and 1173 K (Fig. 1, others vide Supplementary Materials). This accounts for loss of molecular water from the exchange layer “Interlayer Water” and hygroscopicity.

The amount of water uptake of the bentonite sample depends on the relative humidity of the environment to which they are exposed, corresponds to the decarboxylation of the silicate lattice. This is shown as a peak centered at 976 K event in the DTG curve.

The PXRD studies help to understand the diffraction pattern of montmorillonites (vide Supplementary Materials). The mineralogical differences are demonstrated with the help of PXRD and TGA studies. Different levels of alteration are being observed in the bentonite deposits. So investigation of different colours and grades of montmorillonites of Rajmahal Hills and Hazaribag district need PXRD and thermal studies. Thermal studies show weight loss which can easily be compared to the available literature value of the minerals and further studies can be done for defluoridation, removal of heavy metals from aqueous medium. The crystal-chemical

characteristics of the montmorillonite ascertained by PXRD and TGA studies help understand the quality as well as the structure.

It is clear that infrared data (Fig. 2) show peaks at 785.1 cm⁻¹ for MgO, at 978.2 cm⁻¹ for AlO, at 1242 cm⁻¹ for SiO, 3700, 3625 cm⁻¹ for OH- which are similar to montmorillonites, usually having trace of impurities.

Table 6 clearly shows that bentonite mineral may

Fig. 2. FTIR of RHB6.

Table 1. Powdered X-ray diffraction of RHB5

Pos. (°2Th.)	Height (cts)	FWHM (°2Th.)	d-spacing (Å)	Rel. int. (%)
5.9228	1623.66	0.6731	14.92234	99.10
12.3719	1638.41	0.1309	7.15449	100.00
19.8664	753.30	0.2617	4.46919	45.98
24.8903	1052.56	0.1122	3.57735	64.24
36.0054	372.76	0.2991	2.49444	22.75
38.4476	340.62	0.2991	2.34143	20.79
62.3382	238.30	0.7296	1.48831	14.54

Table 2. Powdered X-ray diffraction of RHB6

Pos. (°2Th.)	Height (cts)	FWHM (°2Th.)	d-spacing (Å)	Rel. int. (%)
5.8398	3364.31	0.4861	15.13418	100.00
19.7544	924.00	0.2991	4.49429	27.46
34.8869	232.53	0.8974	2.57181	6.91
61.8692	246.83	0.7296	1.49846	7.34

Table 3. Powdered X-ray diffraction of RB8

Table-4 (contd.)

Pos. (°2Th.)	Height (cts)	FWHM (°2Th.)	d-spacing (Å)	Rel. int. (%)	35.0158	5862.69	0.1870	2.56264	5.31
5.9272	19314.62	0.3365	14.91118	78.22	36.0243	5385.32	0.2244	2.49318	4.88
10.5581	10474.90	0.0561	8.37915	42.42	36.5821	6030.32	0.0561	2.45644	5.46
12.3214	2840.90	0.2991	7.18370	11.51	37.7514	4796.21	0.1122	2.38300	4.34
19.6593	4547.73	0.1496	4.51580	18.42	38.5357	7549.11	0.3365	2.33628	6.84
19.9097	6038.58	0.1496	4.45958	24.45	39.5147	6982.89	0.0561	2.28063	6.32
20.9123	5667.53	0.0748	4.24798	22.95	40.3485	2710.06	0.1496	2.23540	2.45
24.9424	1688.86	0.5983	3.57000	6.84	41.3691	914.15	0.3739	2.18258	0.83
26.3606	7285.51	0.0748	3.38106	29.50	70.2010	1023.45	0.4560	1.33962	0.93
26.6861	19894.48	0.0748	3.34055	80.57	72.3038	1011.73	0.7296	1.30575	0.92
27.2910	10621.96	0.0561	3.26787	43.02	73.6056	1152.40	0.3648	1.28584	1.04
28.6402	24692.63	0.0561	3.11693	100.00	75.6892	2093.27	0.1140	1.25554	1.90
31.8982	3837.53	0.1496	2.80562	15.54	77.7462	847.61	0.3648	1.22738	0.77
33.0802	1184.06	0.2244	2.70803	4.80	79.9471	1431.87	0.4560	1.19903	1.30
35.0189	2408.31	0.2991	2.56242	9.75	81.4928	1349.11	0.1824	1.18015	1.22
38.6361	1174.49	0.4487	2.33044	4.76	83.9255	584.96	0.5472	1.15203	0.53
40.3310	6668.86	0.0561	2.23633	27.01	90.8350	1152.40	0.2736	1.08152	1.04
40.7048	712.73	0.1870	2.21665	2.89	95.2265	464.13	1.0944	1.04290	0.42
41.8143	847.31	0.2244	2.16037	3.43	42.4881	3730.20	0.0748	2.12766	3.38
42.7897	3336.12	0.1122	2.11335	13.51	45.8437	4261.13	0.0561	1.97942	3.86
54.9690	1440.87	0.2244	1.67047	5.84	46.9470	550.88	0.5983	1.93545	0.50
58.2465	2414.75	0.0561	1.58404	9.78	50.1944	63336.42	0.0684	1.81608	57.36
60.0042	2301.23	0.0748	1.54178	9.32	50.3323	32445.63	0.0456	1.81593	29.38
62.2566	1427.26	0.3739	1.49130	5.78	51.0863	1847.02	0.2280	1.78645	1.67
67.9364	400.11	0.7478	1.37980	1.62	54.9197	5179.16	0.0684	1.67047	4.69
75.6801	3387.68	0.0748	1.25670	13.72	56.8504	1398.77	0.3648	1.61824	1.27
79.9332	4343.81	0.0748	1.20020	17.59	58.3824	367.25	0.7296	1.57937	0.33
80.1724	1896.49	0.1368	1.19920	7.68	59.9986	12928.21	0.0684	1.54063	11.71
					60.1648	6733.69	0.0684	1.54059	6.10
					62.3117	4249.22	0.2280	1.48888	3.85
					64.1145	1267.00	0.4560	1.45130	1.15

Table 4. Powdered X-ray diffraction of RB9

Pos. (°2Th.)	Height (cts)	FWHM (°2Th.)	d-spacing (Å)	Rel. int. (%)	65.2630	529.89	0.3648	1.42851	0.48
12.4204	64263.14	0.1122	7.12668	58.20	67.7825	3214.35	0.0912	1.38141	2.91
19.9157	8851.26	0.1309	4.45824	8.02	68.2099	9301.48	0.0684	1.37379	8.42
20.4109	11576.14	0.1122	4.35119	10.48					
20.9081	23773.59	0.0935	4.24882	21.53					
21.2991	10289.34	0.1122	4.17171	9.32					
21.5638	6077.25	0.1122	4.12109	5.50					
23.1460	5443.11	0.1683	3.84284	4.93					
23.8412	2538.23	0.1496	3.73234	2.30					
24.9343	44227.66	0.1496	3.57114	40.05					
26.6842	110426.60	0.0935	3.34079	100.00					
27.4481	4544.66	0.0935	3.24953	4.12					
29.8440	1204.52	0.1870	2.99389	1.09					
30.9087	1163.33	0.2244	2.89314	1.05					

Table 5. Powdered X-ray diffraction of RB10

Pos. (°2Th.)	Height (cts)	FWHM (°2Th.)	d-spacing (Å)	Rel. int. (%)
17.9521	1415.98	0.2244	4.94121	0.95
20.1267	3422.59	0.2617	4.41199	2.30
21.1035	44408.45	0.0748	4.20992	29.80
22.2523	2651.37	0.1496	3.99511	1.78
22.5423	2933.97	0.1122	3.94438	1.97
23.7870	8260.08	0.0935	3.74071	5.54
24.5686	5301.14	0.0748	3.62346	3.56
25.7571	2880.54	0.1496	3.45890	1.93

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Table-5 (contd.)

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26.6923	19868.21	0.0561	3.33980	13.33	70.1291	2949.80	0.3192	1.34082	1.98
26.8822	149038.20	0.1122	3.31663	100.00	73.6542	2727.11	0.1140	1.28511	1.83
27.3694	4188.44	0.1122	3.25869	2.81	75.8634	2544.77	0.0912	1.25309	1.71
27.7070	5477.09	0.1309	3.21975	3.67	77.8363	899.06	0.3648	1.22618	0.60
28.1809	10980.93	0.0748	3.16667	7.37	80.0650	3286.27	0.1140	1.19756	2.20
28.5163	3092.90	0.0935	3.13019	2.08	80.2833	2450.28	0.1140	1.19782	1.64
30.1098	1784.09	0.1496	2.96806	1.20	81.3732	2430.40	0.1140	1.18158	1.63
31.4257	2129.03	0.0748	2.84671	1.43	81.6689	3139.36	0.1140	1.18098	2.11
32.6961	1107.02	0.2244	2.73895	0.74	84.0262	3331.83	0.0912	1.15090	2.24
34.1212	1028.98	0.1496	2.62775	0.69	84.2783	1621.88	0.0912	1.15095	1.09
35.2385	3500.87	0.1870	2.54695	2.35	87.6705	339.57	0.7296	1.11221	0.23
36.7768	23768.15	0.0561	2.44388	15.95	91.0115	2277.55	0.1140	1.07988	1.53
39.6910	7758.76	0.0748	2.27090	5.21	94.8308	2159.73	0.1140	1.04621	1.45
40.5317	4260.70	0.0748	2.22572	2.86	96.4243	1365.50	0.1140	1.03310	0.92
42.6716	17208.82	0.0561	2.11893	11.55	98.8993	1053.53	0.1824	1.01377	0.71
43.0928	1476.37	0.1496	2.09919	0.99					
45.7272	2258.11	0.0748	1.98420	1.52					
46.0175	3901.62	0.2244	1.97235	2.62					
48.3988	2138.23	0.0748	1.88073	1.43					
50.3591	53276.89	0.0684	1.81053	35.75					
50.4975	26998.84	0.0684	1.81037	18.12					
50.7697	2139.90	0.1824	1.79684	1.44					
52.7648	1414.78	0.1824	1.73350	0.95					
55.0994	4895.47	0.0684	1.66545	3.28					
60.1782	10452.72	0.0912	1.53646	7.01					
60.3470	5303.56	0.0912	1.53638	3.56					
61.8826	776.75	0.7296	1.49817	0.52					
64.2282	1813.80	0.0912	1.44900	1.22					
67.9473	5386.20	0.0912	1.37846	3.61					
68.3428	7384.81	0.0912	1.37144	4.95					
68.5238	7076.20	0.1140	1.36826	4.75					

be used for the removal of hexavalent chromium from aqueous medium.

Experimental

Smectite group of minerals have been collected from different places of Rajmahal Hills and tested for montmorillonite by benzidine solution. The mineral has been powdered to 300 μm and dried over 1 h.

The PXRD studies of the samples have been done by using diffractometer type D₈ using Cu as anode material. K-Alpha 1 [Å], K-Alpha 2 [Å] and K-Beta

Table 6. Effect of contact time on adsorption by bentonite

Bentonite sample	50 ml 2 ppm Cr ^{VI} +0.5 g RHB6	Time (min)	Residual amount in ppm
RHB6	"	30	1.86
	"	60	1.26
	"	90	1.82
	"	120	1.68
Bentonite sample	50 ml 2 ppm Cr ^{VI} +0.5 g RHB9	Time (min)	Residual amount in ppm
RHB9	"	30	1.88
	"	60	1.87
	"	90	1.85
	"	120	0.08

[Å] were 1.54060, 1.54443 and 1.39225 respectively. Specimen length was fixed at 10 nm and receiving slit size was 0.100 mm. Studies have been done in Solid and Structural Chemistry Laboratory of IISc, Bangalore.

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